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Research Article

**THE REGULATION WAY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL
COMPLEX TO MAINTAIN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
INTO THE REGION**Elena Sidorchukova¹, Natalia Yaromenko¹, Larisa Petrova², Danil Dudnik³, Marina Sher⁴.¹Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilina, Russia., ²State University of Land Use Planning, Russia., ³North Caucasus branch of the Russian State University of Justice, Russia., ⁴Kuban State University, Russia.**Article Received:** December 2018**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

In the conditions of the formation of new innovation-oriented trends in the world economy, a special place is occupied by the problem of sustainable development of various fields of activity. Not a small role in this is played by the tourism industry, which can bring significant economic benefits to the region. However, maintaining stable growth of this industry is possible only on the basis of activating social, economic, political and environmental indicators. In this regard, the work is devoted to the study of the foundations of sustainable development of the tourism sector on the basis of an effective management mechanism. The functions of state intervention are specified, the structure of the tourism and recreation complex is given. Directions are proposed to increase the pace of sustainable development of tourist activities in selected local systems.

Keywords: *tourism industry, activity, region, economic, environmental indicators.***Corresponding author:****Elena Sidorchukova,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The peculiarity of public administration is to compare the powers of mandatory and recommendatory nature, with the possibility of choosing the option of the necessary solution. The main methods of government in the studied industry include: regulatory and legal regulation of tourist activities; development and implementation of various types of federal, regional and municipal levels; standardization and classification of objects of the tourist industry; information support of tourism, and others. A separate method of administrative and legal

regulation V.M. Munich calls public services, including their preliminary organization. In particular, this is a simulation of the situation in the future, planning services, training, determining the mode of operation and other actions. Accordingly, the provision of public services in the field of tourism, in our opinion, is of no small importance for creating decent conditions for the development of tourism. In this regard, it is possible to single out the following authorities of the state authorities of the Russian Federation in the field of tourism (table 1).

Table 1: Powers of the state authorities of the Russian Federation in the tourism field

The powers of the state authorities of the Russian Federation in the field of tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of the priority direction of tourism development in the Russian Federation; • Development, approval and implementation of federal industry-specific and regional tourism development programs; • Approval of state standards in the field of tourism; • Organization and security of tourism; • Ensuring the implementation of monitoring and statistics in the field of tourism at the federal level; • Exercise of other powers in the field of tourism.
Powers of public authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation in the field of tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting tourism activities and creating an enabling environment for sustainable development; • Provision of state support to tourism industry entities engaged in tourist activities; • Licensing of travel agents for the organization of outbound tourism in the regions of the Russian Federation; • Ensuring the implementation of monitoring in tourism activities at the local level.
Powers of local governments in the field of tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and implementation of tourism development programs; • Determine the direction of development of tourist activities in municipalities; • Implement, within its authority, areas of support for the priority directions of development of the tourism sector in the country; • To promote the products of the tourism industry, formed in the territories of municipalities; • Promote the creation of conditions for the development of the tourism industry.

His influence on the objects of the object of management, by definition V.M. Manokhin, government bodies are expressed in three warrants: state recognition of state regulation and state administration. State recognition means accounting, patronage and protection of objects.

There are many opinions and additions regarding Russian legislation. We, in turn, adhere to the opinion of E. Pisarevsky, who considers the system of legislation on the basis of the following principles:

- consideration of sustainable processes of formation

of society and economic systems;

- direct regulation of tourist relations;
- continuity of the experience of the Soviet regime;
- the adequacy of Russian legislation;
- commensurability with the norms and rules of foreign legislation.

For the tourism industry, as well as for the characteristics of the formation of any regional system, it is important to maintain a sustainable development trend.

In 1999, R. Butler, analyzing the basics of sustainable

tourism development, proposed the following “word for word” definition: sustainable tourism is a form of tourism that ensures its viability for an infinitely long period of time [1, p. 11]. According to the English researcher J. Swarbrook, the definition of sustainable tourism relies on the definition of sustainable development as a whole: sustainable tourism is tourism that meets the needs of today's tourists without prejudice to meeting the needs of the next generations of the local population [6, p. 220]. In 2000, Richard Sharpli noted the underdevelopment of the concept of sustainable tourism and argued for its lack of a sufficiently strong theoretical foundation: this concept is rooted in the concept of sustainable development, but there are no serious scientific works

on the link between sustainable development and tourism and regional development [5, P. 4].

Thus, the state regulation of tourist activity is considered from the point of view of socio-economic and political development as any state-power influence, aimed at activating the system of social and economic relations of society. And the role of government intervention in maintaining sustainable development of the tourism industry is obvious.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

From a theoretical point of view, state regulation is revealed through two directions: functions (Fig. 1) and powers of implementation (table 2).

Table 2: Classifications of government functions in tourism

Function	Implementation tools
1 Organization and control	The introduction of common concepts, definitions; development of procedures for concluding transactions, contracts, obtaining visas; the procedure for passing the border and transportation of goods
2. Planning and forecasting tourism development processes	Development of common strategies and concepts for tourism development; control over the organization of tourist activities and infrastructure development
3. Regulatory and legislative regulation of various types of tourist activities	Standardization, licensing, insurance, certification, provision of financial guarantees
4. Staffing tourism	Creation of standard state programs for the system of continuous training in the field of tourism; assistance to organizations in improving the skills of tourist enterprises
6. Providing scientific research tourism	Marketing research tourism; the creation of regional centers for the study of tourism; information support of tourist enterprises
7. Support for tourism enterprises in the region	Lobbying of interests of a regional tourist complex at the federal level; activation of interregional and international relations; the establishment of representative offices and branches abroad; conclusion of international treaties; advertising regional tourism product
8. Ensuring the safety and security of tourist infrastructure	Creation of rules, laws, conditions of economic incentives for the protection and restoration of natural resources, restoration of historical monuments; distribution of tourist rent; financing of cultural institutions
9. Stimulating the development of tourist activities	Attraction of domestic and foreign sources of financing for the reconstruction and expansion of tourist industry objects

Among the main functions are:

- Development of a scenario for the development of tourist activities in the region;
- Control over compliance with legislation in the field of tourism;
- Control of accounting of offenses of tour operators;
- State standardization and classification (in the field of tourism);

- Logistics;
- Attraction of additional financial sources;
- Raising the level of qualifications of tourism staff.

The implementation of the subtraction functions takes place in the structures of the tourist and recreational complex, which is represented by the following elements (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The structure of the tourist and recreational complex

Specialists of the World Trade Organization, considering the possibilities of Russia as a tourist center, call political stability and economic growth among the most important factors in the development of tourism in our country. At the moment, according to the perspective of the proposed tourist product, Russia is becoming one of the dominant countries, respectively, with the establishment of normal rates, infrastructure development and a rational advertising policy in all segments of the tourism industry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In other states of the Union of Independent States, the situation with inbound tourism is also very promising. About 3.5 million people visited Kazakhstan last year, and almost twice as many in Georgia - about 6.3 million. Such activity statistics in these countries can bring tourism to the position of one of the leading sectors of the economy. World tourism statistics for 2016 by region and country are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Tourism development in 2017 by region and country

Name of the region and its member states	Number of tourists visiting the region / state, million people	% of the total number of tourists in 2016	Travel expenses, billion USD	% of total expenditures of tourists for 2016
North and South America	200	16	240	20
Europe	615	50	504	42
France	84,5	6,8	41	3,4
Spain	68,5	5,5	65,1	5,4
Italy	50,7	4,1	45,5	3,8
Great Britain	31	2,6	64	5,3
Germany	32	2,5	81	6,7
Asia	309	25	216	288
China	56,9	4,6	201	16,7

What Russian and foreign tourists will prefer in 2018 is not yet known, since this is influenced not only by the economic factor, but also by the political one. Prices for consumers are important and people always prefer the most favorable price-quality ratio, but much depends on the political situation in the country and in the world.

The formation of an effective mechanism for the sustainable development of the tourism industry

should take into account the need to develop the regional tourism industry based on the principles of sustainable development. This requires from the state authorities at all levels of management in the development of a strategy for the development of specific tourist regions and the country as a whole, compliance with the fundamental trends of sustainable development (Table 4).

Table 4: Directions for achieving sustainable development of tourism activities

Directions of sustainable development	Direction of activity
Institutional transformations	Formation of new objects of the tourist industry. Maintaining and subsidizing the creation of tourist clusters.
Social development	Improving the welfare of the population, increasing the mobility of the use of tourist resources. Purposeful development of certain types of tourist areas that are most beneficial in the region.
Ecological development	Observation, analysis, consideration of all elements of the environment in determining the most appropriate type and location of tourist facilities.
Information development	Planning, training, public education. Promoting the exchange of information, skills and technologies related to the sustainable development of tourism between developed and developing countries.

Considering modern adaptive mechanisms for the development of tourism as elements of the overall process of long-term sustainable development of tourism in general, it is necessary to include tourism in the overall policies, plans and development models of the respective country and region.

CONCLUSION:

In order to maintain sustainable development, accommodation structures and the tourist industry need to:

- develop health programs, create conditions for the development of medical tourism, because many resorts are equipped with modern medical equipment, existing treatment programs are in demand and provide occupancy in the off-season;
- offer package tours (accommodation, meals, transport component, excursions);
- offer all-inclusive services;
- to ensure the modernization of the material and technical base;
- to diversify tourist products;
- accommodation facilities, beaches and ski slopes get a category on the classification system of tourist industry;
- provide professional development of managerial and service personnel.

Successful implementation of the above and other events will bring the sanatorium-resort and tourist complex of the Krasnodar Territory to a qualitatively higher level of development, provide an opportunity to meet the needs of the population in high-quality spa-resort treatment, interesting recreation and tourism, including foreign tourists.

Achieving these goals will also contribute to the dynamic development of other industries, providing a multiplicative effect on the economy of the Krasnodar Territory, improving socio-economic

indicators and improving the image of the region at the regional and international levels.

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